

Review of standalone small-scale Darrieus wind turbines – a Nottingham case study

Shubham^a, A Ianakiev^a, and N Wright^a

^aDepartment of Civil Engineering, Nottingham Trent University, UK

E-mail: shubham.shubham@ntu.ac.uk

Abstract

A detailed review is conducted on H-rotor Darrieus vertical axis wind turbine. The purpose is to study different designs for urban rooftop applications in the City of Nottingham. Parameters such as aspect ratio, rotor solidity, airfoil profile, preset pitch, innovative blade designs, external structures, etc. are investigated as studied by previous authors. Focus is put on aerodynamic, power performance and also on aeroacoustic studies due to noise limits set in the urban environment and public acceptance. At the end, various areas are mentioned where more studies are needed to make Darrieus VAWT more acceptable and feasible in the urban rooftop settings in Nottingham.

Keywords: Darrieus, Small-scale, Vertical Axis Wind Turbine, Wind resource, Urban environment, Aerodynamics, Power, Aeroacoustics, Noise

1 Introduction

The focus on sustainable development has risen significantly in the past few years. The Paris Agreement 2015 [1] has further intensified investments in renewable energy sector throughout the world such as wind and solar energy. Within the UK, a major source of energy consumption happens within cities either through domestic, services or transport sector [2]. Non-renewable sources contribute a significant part of this energy, thereby keeping the carbon footprint of cities high. The United Nations estimate that from 2018 to 2050, world's urban population will rise by 2.5 billion, or 68% of world's population will live in urban areas from the current 55% [3]. Extensive utilization of renewable sources of energy is therefore needed to foster sustainable urban growth.

Rooftop solar installation is not sufficient for decarbonization goals due to the power vacuum during nighttime and during winter and monsoon seasons when sun days are less. Integrating wind turbines with solar panels on urban rooftops thus becomes a viable alternative. Such standalone off-grid systems also increase efficiency of power generation due to less transmission losses and can play a significant role in the energy transition process [4] [5].

Urban rooftop wind turbines are small-scale in design and operate in wind conditions where the flow is more chaotic and turbulent in nature than in rural or offshore areas [6]. Vertical Axis Wind Turbines (VAWT) are better suited for such wind conditions, as compared to Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWT) [7]. Their advantages include: lower cut-in wind speed and noise, omni-directional in nature and therefore no need of yaw mechanism, higher performance in turbulent and gusty wind conditions. Furthermore, VAWTs have less wear and tear of mechanical components, lower manufacturing costs, simple assembly and installation process and easier maintenance [8] [9], the factors which are very important for its success in the urban environment. VAWTs are further divided into two types: Lift-based Darrieus [10] [11] and Drag-based Savonius [12] [13]. Savonius turbine uses differential drag force for power generation and is less efficient (in terms of energy extracted per unit swept area and Annual Energy Output (AEO)) than Darrieus turbine which utilizes lift generated by airfoil-shaped blades for the same purpose. The design of Darrieus is more complex than Savonius but has more potential to enhance the power generation capability without compromising city noise limits.

In this study, a detailed review is conducted on Darrieus VAWTs and the studies performed so far. Focus will be on aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of such turbines, understanding the effect

of each design parameter on Darrieus performance, and innovative designs that can be taken up in the future.

2 Darrieus VAWT

The basic configuration of a Darrieus VAWT consists of a number of airfoil-shaped blades rotating vertically about an axis perpendicular to the wind direction, as shown in Figure 1 (a) and (b). The Darrieus design is highly dependent on aerodynamic characteristics of such blades. In addition, aeroacoustic behaviour puts additional constraint on such design choices especially for urban rooftop applications. Therefore, it is important to understand the basic aerodynamics to further approach the study of such turbines.

Figure 1: Darrieus VAWT

2.1 Aerodynamic Performance

Over a single rotation from 0° to 360° , blades experience varying Angle of Attack (AoA). The AoA values depend on Blade Speed Ratio (BSR) which in-turn depends on freestream velocity of the wind (V_∞) and rotational velocity of the VAWT (ω). An approximate estimation of AoA and effective velocity (V_{eff}) experienced by the blades can be calculated using simple geometry and is shown in Figure 1 (c) and (d). As BSR increases, maximum and minimum values of AoA in a single rotation decreases.

Highest values are obtained close to the most upstream and downstream position of the blades, which also contributes to higher lift produced. Maximum velocity is experienced at azimuth=0° and minimum velocity at azimuth=180°, when the blade is just entering the upstream and downstream half of the rotation, respectively. VAWT aerodynamics is therefore fundamentally unsteady and the lift produced by the blades is the major contributor to the torque (or power) production, therefore making Darrieus a lift-type VAWT.

Figure 2: Power coefficient vs Tip Speed Ratio curve for a Darrieus VAWT (taken from McIntosh [14])

Figure 2 shows a typical curve for the variation in Darrieus power performance (C_P) with Tip Speed Ratio (also referred to as Blade Speed Ratio (BSR)). In case of lower BSR, AoA values cross the static stall value while approaching the most upstream and downstream point of rotation. Due to constantly changing nature of AoA, blades experience dynamic stall at lower BSR. As BSR increases, the severity of dynamic stall decreases which increases the rotor torque generated. At higher BSR values, parasitic drag on blades become important which in-turn decreases the rotor torque generated. Darrieus VAWT is therefore designed in such a way that it compromises the stall and drag characteristics to maximize performance.

Another important aerodynamic phenomenon is the blade-wake interaction. Blades in the upstream half of rotation generate wake which interacts with the blades in the downstream half, which degrades the performance of blades in the latter half [15]. Generation of tip vortices further intensifies this phenomenon as due to the direction of rotation, wake from top and bottom part of rotor gets deflected towards the mid-span of the downstream blades, as shown by simulations of both Scheurich [16] and Ferreira [17]. This also results in increased unsteady loading fluctuations on rotor blades which can potentially increase the VAWT noise signature.

2.2 Historical development of Darrieus configurations

A detailed chronological sequence of various Darrieus configurations is shown by Tjiu [11]. Darrieus VAWT was initially proposed by Darrieus in 1925, the design of which is shown in Figure 3 from his 1931 patent [18]. Both the curved and straight-bladed Darrieus evolved through the 2nd half of 20th century when a number of designs were experimented. In case of curved blades, Guy-wired phi (ϕ) rotor was experimented from 1968-early 1990s. The rotors were large-scale ranging from 30-500 kW, even going towards 2.5-4 MW (largest VAWT in the world by NRC Canada) from 1988-93. Following the lessons learnt from these designs and some failures happening in 1978-81, the design evolved towards Fixed on tower/Cantilevered phi (ϕ) rotor from 2000s-present, especially in USA and Canada.

In case of straight blades, initially large-scale rotors were experimented. Variable-geometry (Musgrove) and Variable-pitch (Giromill) rotors evolved during 1970s-80s. A number of problems arose with these configurations such as high manufacturing cost, high COE (Cost of Operation) and less competitive nature in the market. After a review on the wind turbine technology by Musgrove [19] [20] and his efforts into designing a simpler VAWT, straight-bladed Darrieus became more common after 1988. The design further evolved into Fixed-pitch H-rotor which had a similar design to the 1931 patent by Darrieus. Large-scale H-rotor proved to be quite costly as compared to its HAWT counterpart, therefore a number of small-scale H-rotor and its variations started coming up in 2000s, such as Articulating and Helical

Figure 3: Design of Darrieus VAWT proposed in 1931 patent [18]; left: curved-bladed, right: straight-bladed; a: blades, e: supporting plates, f and g: rotor shaft, f1 and f2: hubs

H-rotor. Small-scale design allowed the researchers to easily experiment with different design parameters at a relatively lower cost. This paper focuses purely on small-scale Darrieus H-rotor and the research performed till now on its design and analysis.

3 H-rotor: State of the Art

Most of the research is focussed on to increase the power production of Darrieus turbine by increasing the lift on blades and decreasing the drag forces [10] [21] [22]. Small-scale design allows the flexibility to chose from multiple geometrical parameters for efficient operation of the VAWT in turbulent and comparatively scarce urban wind resource. Since the VAWT will be placed in built-up areas, a major focus is also towards reducing the noise produced by a Darrieus turbine [23] [24] [25]. This will go a long way in public acceptance of such sustainable energy systems [26] [27].

3.1 Aerodynamics and Performance analysis

Since a multitude of design parameters are available for a Darrieus rotor, it is important to understand the effect of each on overall torque/power production of the rotor to design an optimum wind turbine. Such parameters include Aspect Ratio, Solidity, Airfoil Profile, Preset Pitch, Blade Design, etc. examined over a range of Blade Speed Ratio (BSR), both experimentally and numerically.

3.1.1 Experimental benchmark studies

Kaushik [9] provides a review of experiments conducted on various designs of Darrieus rotor. Blackwell [28] presents a detailed wind tunnel performance data for the Darrieus wind turbine with NACA 0012 blades for different wind velocities, rotational speed, solidities and Reynolds number. Battisti [29] examines both H-shaped and troposkien Darrieus rotor using experimental methods, compares their aerodynamic performance and provides a benchmark for validation of computational tools. Previously, Battisti [30] performed wind tunnel measurements on a H-rotor and examines the effect of blockage and full 3D flow features including tip vortices effect. Howell [8] tested a small-scale H-rotor for different wind velocities, BSR, solidities (2-bladed and 3-bladed rotor) and rotor blade surface finish, while making comparisons with 2D and 3D CFD results. Li [31] investigated the effects of ice and snow attached to the rotor blades, on Darrieus rotor power performance. This assumes special significance in the northern UK and north-western Europe, where there is significant snowfall in cold climates. Fiedler [32] investigated a high-solidity 3-bladed Darrieus H-rotor to study the effects of blade pitch, both positive and negative values, and blade mount-point offset on VAWT performance. LeBlanc [33] [34] presented an experimental benchmark to validate studies on using active variable pitch on individual rotor blades.

3.1.2 Aspect Ratio

Aspect Ratio (AR) for a Darrieus VAWT is defined as the ratio of rotor span with rotor diameter. This is also related to the AR of airfoil blades used. Ghonim [35] showed that an optimum value of AR is required to get the maximum C_P value; for $V_\infty = 10$ m/sec the value of AR is 1.3 for a 3-bladed Darrieus H-rotor. The reason is: a higher AR rotor will help in reducing the adverse effect of tip vortices on rotor blade loads, thus potentially producing higher rotor torque and requiring lower BSR values [15]. Although,

higher AR requires higher structural strength of the rotor, thus requiring a number of supporting struts as can be seen for WindSpire turbine [36]. This increases the parasitic drag and also turbulence content in the rotor wake. Due to increased interaction between downstream blades and higher turbulent wake, there is a potential decrease in torque. An optimum value of AR is also required for a good self-starting capability. This is shown by opposite conclusions of Ghonim [35] who proposed to decrease AR, and Du [37] who proposed to increase AR, for increasing the self-starting capability of the rotor at lower wind velocities. Brusca [38] highlighted similar results to the former by showing that lower AR rotor produces higher power coefficients due to higher blade Reynolds number. This can help in self-starting of the rotor and also provide higher structural stability.

3.1.3 Solidity

VAWT solidity is defined as the ratio of blade area to rotor swept area, which signifies the level of blockage rotor blades provide for the oncoming flow. Mathematically, it is defined as $\sigma = Nc/R$, where σ is VAWT solidity, N is number of blades, c is blade chord and R is rotor radius. Mohamed [39] simulated S-1046 airfoil for solidities ranging from 0.1-0.25. Higher solidities performed better (higher C_P) at lower BSR values and lower solidities performed better at higher BSR values, which is also shown by Howell [8]. When solidity increases, stronger wake is produced which leads to more blade-wake interaction. This is more stronger at higher BSR values, which leads to lower rotor performance. Therefore, adding blades (increasing solidity) reduces optimum rotor performance. The results also show that self-starting can be improved with high-solidity rotors (due to higher C_P at low BSR), although this will compromise the higher BSR performance where the Darrieus rotor may operate for majority of its service life. A good work on self-starting capability is done by Baker [40], Dominy [41] and Hill [42]. On the other hand, lower solidities provide higher operating range for any Darrieus rotor which makes it more suitable for urban environments where wind velocities vary significantly. Also, the power curve is smoother around the optimum TSR point (highest C_P), so easier for the control system to operate around that point [43]. The design of Darrieus is therefore a compromise between self-starting characteristics (low BSR) and higher operating range (mid to high BSR). For a city like Nottingham which has a mix of both congested and open spaces within the inner city limits, this design compromise assumes special relevance for different localities.

3.1.4 Airfoil Profile

The choice of airfoil profile can significantly affect the power and noise output of a Darrieus turbine. Since the AoA perceived by the blade varies from both positive and negative values, symmetrical airfoil are commonly used such as NACA 00XX series. Mohamed [39] simulated 20 different airfoil shapes using URANS simulation. In case of symmetrical NACA series, maximum C_P of 0.2964 was obtained by NACA 0018. Lower thickness airfoil perform better at higher BSR values while higher thickness airfoil perform better at lower BSR values. Same conclusion was obtained by Roh [44] and Healy [45]. Additionally, non-symmetrical airfoils were also simulated by Mohamed [39] and it was shown that symmetrical airfoils both performed better and has higher operating range than the former. The main reason being, symmetrical airfoils delay stall, thus reducing the adverse effects on blade loads. Highest C_P value amongst all 20 airfoils was obtained for S-1046 airfoil.

3.1.5 Preset Pitch

Preset pitch is defined as the angle between Darrieus blade chord line and tangent line to the circumferential path of the rotor blade. Similar to the reasons in case of airfoil profile, the preset pitch is normally kept at 0° , although positive or negative angles in some cases can lead to higher C_P values. Armstrong [46] experimented with 3-bladed H-rotor with NACA 0015 profile. C_P value increased by 15% if preset pitch was changed from 0° to -6° i.e toe-out position and this happens due to a change in AoA perceived by the blades. Toe-out reduces the AoA on upwind part and increases on downwind part, and a balance between the optimum AoAs decides the overall change in performance. Generally, performance increases upto a value of toe-out angle and then decreases. A number of authors such as LeBlanc [33] [34] and Tavernier [47] have also suggested using active variable pitch for individual blades, to improve power extraction by creating optimal loading and minimizing losses at every azimuthal locations. The same

method can also be used to control the direction of rotor wake for wind farm control and structural fatigue reasons [48].

3.1.6 Blade Design

As seen in previous discussions, straight-bladed rotor designs (H-rotor) are most common as they are easier and less costly to manufacture and maintain. Additionally, innovative blade designs can be used to increase the C_P values while having negligible impact on aerodynamic noise and mechanical bearing loads of the Darrieus turbine. Helical-bladed Darrieus rotor, as in the case of Quiet Revolution [49], provides multiple benefits such as slightly higher effective chord, smoother blade loads or driving torque in a single rotation which can help to reduce mechanical vibrations and aerodynamic noise produced. It also improves aesthetics which is important for public acceptance. A similar design was experimented by Bussel [50] in 2004, named as TURBY, which is designed specifically for the built environment. Although, helical blades are expensive to manufacture than simple straight blades [7]. A number of authors use zig-zag trip, both on the suction and pressure side of the blade, to force boundary-layer transition at a specific chord location [15]. This helps to reduce flow separation which in-turn increases power performance and reduces laminar boundary layer noise [51]. Another commonly experimented blade design is the 3D troposkien shape [29] which gives better performance than straight-bladed rotor at higher BSR values. Different available blade designs make it imperative to compare individual performances for a given wind velocity at the desired urban location.

3.1.7 Special structures for Darrieus VAWT

A few authors experimented with additional structures placed around the Darrieus rotor to increase its power performance. The concept is similar to ducted HAWT in which the rotor is shrouded by a diffuser to direct the oncoming flow direction. Kim [52] placed a flat plate deflector in front of a pair of counter-rotating Darrieus rotors, which increased the flow velocity on each rotor by 10-30% more than the freestream velocity. Longer and narrower deflector produced higher C_P values (2-3 times) than shorter and wider deflector. Also, closer the rotors were to the deflector (in the streamwise direction), higher the values of C_P were. One major drawback of using such structures is that it makes the turbine more directional, which can be disadvantageous in an urban setting.

3.2 Aeroacoustic studies

Since the focus is on urban wind turbines in Nottingham, UK, reduction of Darrieus noise signature assumes relevance. This is also coupled to strict regulations imposed by Nottingham City Council for the noise limits in a crowded built-up urban locality. The major source of noise in a Darrieus turbine is the unsteady loading on rotor blades due to the interaction of solid blades and air flow around it. A number of studies have been undertaken to understand the Darrieus noise generation mechanisms and methods to reduce its acoustic signature.

Dumitrescu [53] compared noise for a HAWT and a VAWT at similar power performance ($C_P=0.4$) and found that the latter produced less overall noise (47 dB) than the former (56 dB). Pearson [15] experimented with 3-bladed Darrieus H-rotor, for different BSRs, freestream velocities, rotational speeds and solidities. Higher harmonic content was found in case of lower BSR values, due to dynamic stall being dominant at lower rotational speeds and at blade loading harmonics (dynamic stall is periodic in nature). At higher BSR, BVI is a bigger noise source which is more stochastic in nature. Increasing solidity (number of blades) decreases harmonic content. This happens due to decrease in Angle of Attack (AoA) on blades in the upstream half of rotation and therefore, dynamic stall, as solidity increases. Increase in turbulence inflow leads to a reduction in harmonic content in the noise spectra due to periodic loading being disrupted by stochastic loading of turbulent eddies on Darrieus blades. Using Boundary Layer (BL) trips on both the outer and inner blade surfaces can avoid the laminar BL noise. A general trend was found that noise decreases with increase in BSR due to increase in induction factor. This rate of increase or decrease is higher for high solidity rotors due to its higher induction factors. This means that off-design penalty for noise will be more for high solidity rotors, which is similar to the penalties in aerodynamics. This makes turbine control significant for such rotors especially in regions of rapidly varying wind speeds.

Gocmen [54] optimized 6 different airfoils, such as FX 63-137, S822, S834, etc. both for noise and power performance. Generally speaking, reducing airfoil thickness and increasing camber helps to reduce noise and increase the ratio of lift/drag over a range of AoA. Weber [55] tested a 3-bladed H-rotor and showed that in a flowfield, some major noise sources are present around vortices generated in the wake, flow separation over blades and karman vortices behind the turbine shaft. BPF noise is mainly caused due to Blade-Vortex Interaction (BVI) and unsteady loading on the blade. Changing lift and drag forces on a blade in a single rotation is also a source of loading noise and contributes to higher harmonics. Mohamed [56] simulated a 3-bladed H-rotor with different airfoils, with S-1046 producing the lowest noise. Increasing BSR and solidity both contributed to increased overall noise, due to higher BVI and unsteady loading on blades. The findings for increasing BSR values is opposite to what is mentioned by Pearson [15]. This shows that there will be an optimum value of BSR where the noise will be maximum or minimum.

Higher AR can also lead to increase in noise generated due to increased blade-wake interaction [15]. Availability of vertical space and wind resource in urban locality can also play a significant role in the same [57]. Venkatraman [58] simulated noise generated due to flow non-uniformity experienced by a Darrieus turbine on an urban rooftop. The directivity of overall sound increases in the direction of the velocity gradient with a little increase in higher BPF and broadband noise. Understanding such behaviour is important to figure out the noise impact of rooftop wind turbines. There is a potential to design Darrieus turbines with directivity opposite to humans settlements.

4 Conclusions and future scope

In this study, a detailed review was conducted for H-rotor Darrieus VAWT. After the first design in 1925, a significant amount of research has been conducted on the aerodynamic design and analysis of such turbines. Initially, the focus was on large scale design for multi-megawatt applications. In the 21st century, the focus has shifted towards small-scale applications in urban settings. Small-scale turbine allows to easily experiment with different design parameters to achieve the highest performance for a given wind resource. Overall, there is sufficient work done on performance analysis of such turbines. In the coming years, there is a need to understand the detailed flow physics of a Darrieus turbine. Studies on AoA variation, flow separation, dynamic stall, blade-wake interaction, Reynolds number effect are needed. Power performance analysis is required in case of oblique wind conditions, turbulent inflow, wind gusts, etc.

Since the aim is to install wind turbines on rooftops, special focus is needed to reduce the noise signature of such machines due to close proximity with humans. For that, studies are needed to understand the noise generation mechanisms and methods to mitigate them. Apart from high-fidelity computational studies, low-fidelity analyses are also needed to understand each of those mechanism separately and focus on the most relevant ones. New innovative Darrieus designs can be taken up, such as blade tips to mitigate tip vortices, trailing-edge serrations, external structures around VAWT, helical blades, etc. Darrieus clusters can be investigated which can enhance the power generation capacity on a single rooftop. The objective will be to lower community noise generation without impacting the power generation capacity of a wind turbine. This will go a long way in increasing public adoption of small-scale urban vertical axis wind turbines.

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